

GLOMERULAR KIDNEY LESIONS IN ONCOLOGICAL DISEASES AND THEIR TREATMENT.

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Relevance. In modern nephrology, a close relationship has been established between the development of glomerular pathologies and various types of malignant neoplasms, including both solid tumors and hematological forms. Scientific studies demonstrate certain patterns in the occurrence of specific types of glomerulopathies in different oncological diseases. In particular, membranous nephropathy is more commonly diagnosed in cases of solid tumors, whereas in hematological malignancies—especially non-Hodgkin lymphoma—minimal change disease is predominantly observed.

Research objective: The research material consisted of medical data from 120 women with a verified diagnosis of breast cancer at stage pT3-4N2M1, who underwent palliative treatment between 2015 and 2025 at the Tashkent City Branch of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Oncology and Radiology (RSSPMCOR). The patients according to various regimens: AC/CAF/FAC, AC + paclitaxel, gemcitabine, and liposomal doxorubicin.

As part of the study, a comparative analysis was conducted between traditional biomarkers (creatinine, urea, creatinine clearance) and novel biomarkers of nephrotoxicity. The choice of stage T3-4N2M1 for the study was driven by the need to examine the diversity of clinical manifestations and prognostic parameters within the same stage of oncological disease. To assess nephrotoxicity, the NGAL (Neutrophil Gelatinase-Associated Lipocalin) test was used—a kit for the quantitative determination of neutrophil gelatinase-associated lipocalin concentration in plasma. The principle of the Finecare™ NGAL Rapid Quantitative Test is based on fluorescent immunoassay technology and utilizes the sandwich immunodetection method.

Results: It was found that the novel biomarkers (NGAL and IL-6) show statistically significant changes within 24–48 hours after the administration of chemotherapeutic agents, which is 2–4 days earlier than the dynamics of traditional renal function markers. Differences in the nephrotoxic potential of the studied chemotherapy regimens were identified. The most pronounced changes in renal function were observed with gemcitabine and the AC +

paclitaxel regimen, while the regimen with liposomal doxorubicin was found to be the least nephrotoxic. The high diagnostic value of NGAL for the early detection of acute kidney injury (AKI) has been demonstrated: Sensitivity: 88.9% Specificity: 86.7% Accuracy: 87.5% Positive predictive value: 80.0%. A strong correlation was established between the novel biomarkers (NGAL and IL-6) and the clinical manifestations of nephrotoxicity ($r = 0.72-0.75$, $p < 0.001$).

Conclusions: The conducted study revealed the significant diagnostic value of biomarkers such as neutrophil gelatinase-associated lipocalin (NGAL) and interleukin-6 (IL-6) for the early detection of nephrotoxicity. For NGAL, the following diagnostic characteristics were determined: Sensitivity was 88.9%, indicating a high likelihood of a positive result in the presence of nephrotoxicity. Specificity reached 86.7%, demonstrating its ability to accurately distinguish cases of nephrotoxicity from those without it. The overall diagnostic accuracy of the NGAL test was 87.5%, and the positive predictive value reached 94.1%, highlighting its high effectiveness as a diagnostic marker.

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